

POLAC JOURNAL OF SOCIAL AND MANAGEMENT SCIENCES (PJSMS)

Vol. 3 No. 2 September, 2025

ISSN - Print: 2992-5009; Online: 2437-1246

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A Multi-State Survey of Security Personnel on Violent Conflicts and the Challenges of Control in Northern Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined violent conflicts and the challenges of control in northern Nigeria, with a particular focus on determining whether the challenges faced by security agencies are consistent across the affected states. To achieve this, the survey was used as the research design. Routine activity theory was adopted as the theoretical guide. Purposive sampling was used to recruit participants from a population of security personnel who provide security services in conflict zones in northern Nigeria. Online questionnaires and in-depth interviews were used to collect respondents' views on the challenges they face in attempting to control violent conflict in northern Nigeria. Simple percentage and chi-square analytical tools were used to analyse the quantitative data derived from the study, while a thematic/content analytical approach was used to analyze the qualitative data. Result from the test of hypothesis was significant since the p-value was less than .05. The outcome was $\chi^2 = (1, N = 67) = 60.896^a$, $df = 10$, $p = .000$. Based on this, the alternate hypothesis which states that the main challenges confronting security agencies in their attempts to control violent conflict vary significantly in the affected communities of Northern Nigeria. Findings indicated that the main challenges confronting the security agencies in their bid to control violent conflicts in northern Nigeria include: political interference, corruption, lack of operational facilities, and sabotage from members of the public who serve as informants to terrorists/insurgents. Consequent upon these, the study recommended, among other things, that the government should focus more on identifying the political actors who intervene in the process of law enforcement against the perpetrators of violent conflict to serve as a deterrent to others. This is because much has been said about the political actors who sponsor the violent conflicts in the region, but less is heard about their arrest and punishment.

Keywords: Violent, Conflict, Challenges, Northern Region, Nigeria.

Article history:

Received: 27 June 2025

Reviewed: 20 July 2025

Accepted: 29 September 2025

About the Journal: PJSMS is a multidisciplinary journal and the official journal of the Faculty of Social and Management Sciences, Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil-Kano, Nigeria, published biannually.

Abraham, U. E. (2025).

A Multi-State Survey of Security Personnel on Violent Conflicts and the Challenges of Control in Northern Nigeria**Introduction**

In recent times, violent conflicts have characterized the Nigerian state. The prevalence of these conflicts has cost the country in many dimensions. Very worrisome is the loss of human lives and property, and the huge financial implications on annual budgets. There is no part of the country that is free, as each state or geopolitical zone has its peculiar circumstances (Odivwri and Abraham, 2015). However, recent reports show that the northern part of the country is the worst hit by violent conflicts (Ugbodaga, 2023; Ukoji and Ukoji, 2023; World Report, 2023; Nigeria Watch, 2022). Prominently, the region is faced with the problems of the Boko Haram terrorist group, banditry, kidnapping, and herders-farmers conflict. For more than a decade now, these groups/activities have consistently put the northern region at the forefront of violent conflicts.

Statistically, recent happenings in 2023 indicated that violent conflicts in the region claimed the lives of 7,057 people. As reported, the North-East geopolitical zone had the highest number of killings with 3,271 deaths (four killings per event); the North-West zone recorded 2,073 killings with 2.1 killings per event recorded; while the North-Central zone had 1,713 killings recorded with 2 killings recorded per event (Ogunyemi, 2024). This is an increase from what was recorded in 2021(6,271), but a slight decrease from what was obtainable in 2022 (7,564) (Nigeria Watch, 2021; 2022). On the whole, the region is said to account for 77% of the overall fatalities recorded, compared to other regions of the country (Nigeria Watch, 2022).

In an attempt to find a lasting solution to these conflicts, and as well restore peace in the affected communities, the government has utilized various measures to address these problems. Prominent among the strategies is the deployment of combined troops from the military and the police force to the affected communities to help maintain peace and order. To aid their operations, the government

has also supplied logistics such as financial support, operational vehicles, and sophisticated weapons to boost their performance. Similarly, members of the public in the affected communities have also contributed by forming informal police structures (vigilante groups) to support the efforts of the government to check the menace (Nadama, 2019). Yet, these conflicts are still rampant, and more worrisome is that they are escalating daily, and many people are killed, raped, and kidnapped for ransom, while their cattle are rustled, and their property is destroyed as well. This has raised concerns about the effectiveness of our security institutions in addressing these problems, particularly the challenges they face in attempting to control the menace.

Also, there is a dearth of studies on the main challenges confronting the security agencies in their attempt to control violent conflicts in northern Nigeria, despite the huge amount of money budgeted annually for defence and security. The little seen in the literature are studies on individual states (Abraham and Sakariyau, 2023; Saye and Abraham, 2019) with no attempts to examine the situation on a large scale as it affects the entire northern region of Nigeria. These research gaps necessitated this study, which investigated the main challenges confronting security agencies deployed for control of violent conflicts in northern Nigeria. This was imperative because despite the huge sum of money budgeted for security on an annual basis in the country, and the billions of naira allocated to Northern Nigeria as security votes, violent conflicts keep persisting at a very alarming rate, and daily, people are killed, kidnapped for ransom, while their properties are destroyed with great impacts on the socioeconomic development of the region.

Statement of the Problem

Violent conflict has become a major bane to the attainment of peace in Northern Nigeria. Frequently, there are reports of bandits' attacks, cattle rustling, Boko Haram terrorists'

attacks, herders-farmers clashes, ethno-religious crisis, and, very recently, kidnapping for ransom. Consequently, Nigerians living in the region are killed, raped, kidnapped, and their property destroyed, while they constantly live in fear because they do not know who will be the next victim. Also, agricultural activity, which is the mainstay of the economy, is affected, while the security and peace of the region are undermined. The government, as reported, has responded by building new military barracks and police posts in the affected areas. Also, security personnel have been deployed in numbers to the affected communities to help maintain peace and order. This is in addition to the huge sum of money budgeted annually for security at both the state and federal government levels. Yet despite all these, violent conflicts are still on the increase, instead of declining in Northern Nigeria. The deployment of security personnel to the region is basically to help address these problems. However, it is surprising that despite the continuous deployment of security men, together with their purported onslaughts against the perpetrators of the violent conflicts, Nigerians living in the region are still reported killed, kidnapped, raped, and their property and means of livelihood destroyed at a very alarming rate. This raises concerns about the effectiveness of our security institutions in addressing the problem.

Furthermore, despite the various research on violent conflicts in the region, there is a dearth of studies on the main challenges confronting security agencies deployed to ensure control. What is obvious in the literature are studies on specific communities, states, and geopolitical zones in Northern Nigeria, and the prevalent conflicts in their domains. Very little or scanty work is seen on violent conflicts, as they affect the entire region. Therefore, it is on this basis that this study emerged to examine the problems holistically as they affect the entire region, irrespective of peculiarity in communities, states, or geopolitical zones within the region. Special focus was on the challenges confronting the security agencies in their attempts to control the situation in the region. The essence is to establish if the

challenges faced by the security agencies are the same across the affected states/communities in the region.

Literature Review

Challenges confronting Security Agencies in their attempts to Control Violent Conflicts

There are many challenges militating against the effective control of violent conflicts in Nigeria. These challenges are:

1. Corruption

Corruption is a cankerworm bedeviling Nigeria for a very long time. It permeates all sectors, including the security agencies. Apparently, on our roads/highways, men and officers of the Nigeria Police Force and the Nigeria Road Safety Corps are seen openly extorting money from commercial and personal drivers (Inyang and Abraham, 2013). This illicit act allows vehicles to pass without proper checks (Isah and Musa, 2023). In the process, sophisticated weapons are allowed to pass the roads easily into the hands of insurgents who then use them for criminal activities (Sule, Mikail, and Yahaya, 2020). This may contribute significantly to the proliferation of arms and the use of arms in conflict situations, bedeviling the country.

Apart from this show of shame on the highways, there are other cases of corruption that are detrimental to the security of the country, and such cases are practised covertly. A typical example is the case of a former National Security Adviser of the country, Mr Sambo Dasuki, who was accused of arms fraud amounting to the sum of \$2billion. As reported, Mr Dasuki was given a huge sum to help acquire military equipment for the fight against Boko Haram militants, but the money was not judiciously used to acquire the desired equipment (BBC, 2015). These illegal acts have compromised security plans and have thwarted efforts to tackle insurgency and other violent crimes in Nigeria. It also underscores the fact that resources have been committed to addressing security threats in the country; however, the process is sometimes plagued by significant corruption (Gulleng, 2025).

2. Poor Intelligence Gathering/Sharing

One factor that affects partnerships to control crime is poor intelligence gathering and sharing among law enforcement agencies in Nigeria (Abraham and Sakariyau, 2023). As observed by Oluwafemi, Balogun, and Layefa (2019), this has contributed to the ineffectiveness or lack of pro-activeness among security agencies in their response to insurgency and banditry in the country, and it is a setback in the country's effort to crush the insurgents and overcome the associated challenges (Isah and Musa, 2023). Sometimes, instead of interagency collaboration, individual agencies try to showcase personal effort in situations where partnerships would have aided success. This constitutes a serious bane to the fight against insurgency and banditry in the country (Abraham, 2022).

3. Lack of Inter-agency Collaboration among Security Agencies

Another factor that hinders the effective control of violent crimes in Nigeria is the lack of synergy among security agencies (Isah and Musa, 2023; Abraham, 2022). This has led to intelligence failure, rivalry among agencies, and the enablement of insurgents to cause more havoc in society (Bamidele, 2012). Isah and Musa (2023) argued that, instead of security agencies forming collaborations to tackle the enormous crime problems affecting the country, they are engulfed in unhealthy rivalries. These rivalries are noticed between the police and the Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps (NSCDC), police and the Department of State Service (DSS), Police and the Military, and Police and local vigilante groups (Abraham 2022). The overall effect of this interagency rivalry is the inability of Nigeria's security sector to proffer a workable solution to the lingering security problems ravaging the country (Isah and Musa, 2023). This inability to come together and work together cripples effective crime control.

4. Porous Borders

Nigeria has over 1,400 illegal routes, according to the former Immigration Head David Parrandang (Abayomi, 2024). Out of this number, Ogun and Adamawa states, for

example, have 83 and 80 illegal routes respectively (Monguno, 2021). This constitutes another challenge militating against the effective control of violent crimes in the country, as these illegal routes serve as an avenue for terrorists and smugglers to move in Small Arms and Light Weapons (SALWs) into the country (Abayomi, 2024; Eselebo and Okunade, 2021). As described by Isah and Musa (2023), the country's borders are flexible, and this enables easy access into the country, with significant impacts on the fight against insurgency and banditry. This is why the Centre for Democracy and Development (2022) reported that foreign militias take advantage of the porosity of our borders to migrate illegally into the country, form alliances with the local militia, and supply them arms to fight the state. Consequently, the state finds it difficult to apprehend them because of the availability of many routes made possible by the porous borders for escape. This, probably, may be one of the reasons the fight against insurgency and banditry is continuous and difficult to control.

5. Political Interference

Political interference also militates against the efforts of security agencies to control violent conflict in Nigeria. This is confirmed by some of the comments and actions of the political actors. Recently, the governor of Zamfara state, Dauda Lawal, in an interview with Channels TV, stated that there is so much political interference that does not allow the military and other security agencies to do their work effectively. According to him, "the military and other security agencies have the capability to take care of these security threats if there is no political interference; the continuous interference from the political class makes the problem linger" (Aleke and Dipo, 2024). Although the governor did not discuss the kind of interference exhibited by the political class, Isah and Musa (2023) linked it to the frequent change of service chiefs, which has affected the fight against insurgency and terrorism. According to them, political actors do not allow the personnel to grow through the ranks; they continue changing the service chiefs because of

perceived loyalty and political alignment. This becomes a major hindrance to the fight against insurgency.

6. Lack of Modern Operational Facilities

Lack of modern equipment has been an issue of concern for too long in the fight against insurgency and terrorism in Nigeria. Every year, the government keeps budgeting huge funds for the purchase of equipment to fight insurgency and other violent crimes in the country, but laxity in the implementation process has always been the bane of delivering what was budgeted for (Abraham and Sakariyau, 2023). This is why we have cases of corruption reported against some of the senior government officials who are engaged in the purchasing of military aircraft and equipment (BBC, 2015; Torulagha, 2006). Isah and Musa (2023) observed that, in most cases, the weapons provided to the military who are on the frontline in the fight against terrorism and insurgency in the country are obsolete or less sophisticated when compared to the ones the terrorists operate with. Probably, this may be the reason the terrorists appear better organized, motivated, and logically organized, while our military looks exposed and overwhelmed by the insurgents in the ongoing battle.

7. Lack of Support from the Host Communities

In the ongoing war against terrorism and insurgency, there are reports about host communities refusing to give support by cooperating with the security agencies and giving information that is needed to help apprehend the enemies of the state (Isah and Musa, 2023). This kind of scenario is what made the former governor of Zamfara state, Bello Matawalle, publicly call out the Emir of Maru and the District Head of Kanoma for allegedly giving support to the bandits, at the detriment of the state (Bilesamni, 2021). The reason for this allegiance to the bandits, as revealed by Abraham and Sakariyau (2023) in their study of banditry in the northwest zone of the country, is that most of the community members see the terrorists/insurgents as their brothers, uncles, and neighbours. Therefore, they develop sympathy for them, shield them from arrest, and also serve as informants to

them about the activities of the state actors in their terrain.

In other instances, it is reported that the militants gain the support of community members by promising them financial assistance, welfare, and protection (Mercy Corps, 2016). This is possible because of the inadequacies on the part of the government to provide basic services to the people. Where the people do not feel the impact of the government in regard to their welfare, better offers from the militants become attractive. However, in situations where the community members express doubts, the insurgents use force and threaten to kill them if they are exposed to security agencies – a strategy that makes the community members stay loyal to the insurgents, and their detects, instead of being patriotic to the state (Centre for Democracy and Development, 2022).

8. Inadequate Manpower

The effort of the Nigerian state to fight insurgency and terrorism has also been hampered by inadequate manpower (Abraham, 2022). Presently, there has been a combined team of security forces (locally and internationally) to boost the personnel strength of the state against the enemies (Isah and Musa, 2023). However, the military, which is at the forefront of the counter-terrorism/insurgency initiative, has been reported to be overstretched because of the enormous security challenges that have been duplicated across all regions of the country that demand military intervention (Abraham, 2025). Apart from this, the few who are left are killed frequently on the battlefield, some have been seriously injured and incapacitated, while others have retired from service, thereby adding to the already depleted number of security personnel to engage the insurgents/terrorists (Hussain, Okeke, Oyebanyi, Akunne, and Omoruyi, 2021). This is why there have been calls for the government to consider bringing back the retired but not tired ex-military and policemen, or engage mercenaries who are willing to join the fight to boost the existing strength of its security forces against the enemies of the state (DRN, 2025; Nwabughio, 2021). However, what is

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

demotivating is that the existing personnel engaged in the battlefield are facing setbacks that are affecting their capacity. These setbacks are: lack of morale, overstretched deployment, lack of modern equipment, and corruption (Dauda and Opeyeoluwa, 2023).

9. Poor Welfare

Poor welfare has been reported as another impediment confronting the efforts of security agencies to control insurgency/terrorism in Nigeria. This leads to decreased morale, motivation, and discipline. It also diminishes the effectiveness in combat and intelligence gathering (Ike, Jidong, Ike, and Ayobi, 2024). Where this happens, the operational effectiveness of the security forces to tackle security threats will be hindered, while the terrorists/insurgents will be motivated to cause more mayhem in the state and gain control of more territories (Dauda and Opeyeoluwa, 2023). In response, the Nigerian government has made efforts to improve the welfare of its security personnel in order to motivate them and boost their morale to counter the enormous security threats. This is evident in increased salaries and financial benefits extended to deceased soldiers' families (Nnodim, 2024; Majeed, 2024; Ministry of Defence, 2020). However, the sufficiency of these packages, and the extent they have gone to boost the morale of the security personnel in their fight against terrorism and insurgency, are yet to be measured.

10. Faulty Recruitment and Lack of Training on Counter Terrorism and Insurgency

Faulty recruitment and lack of effective training are seen as primary areas that pose some challenges to the capacity and capability of Nigeria's security institutions (Ijide, 2020). The recruitment process is often compromised through acts of corruption: nepotism and favouritism (UNODC, 2020). This gives room for unsuitable candidates to be recruited through the back door because they have 'godfathers' who pushed for them to be taken. The majority of those who adopt this means mostly do not attend the interviews for the job, and even if they attend, they mostly do not perform well. However, they are the ones

given the job, while those who performed better during the interview are dropped (NAN, 2022). The consequence is that this act of corruption has given room for unqualified persons to be recruited into the security institutions. This crop of persons represents misfits who cannot deliver when duty calls, and they pose a danger to society because they lack the capacity for the job (Ijide, 2020).

Training is supposed to correct some of the anomalies created by the faulty recruitment process. However, the training institutions are short of facilities and instructors, training modules, and are largely dependent on conventional operations instead of specialized skills to counter the current security threats (Ijide, 2020). This is why some security personnel have difficulties in their efforts to counter terrorism/insurgency in the country. There is a deficiency in specialized training, and there is heavy reliance on kenotic military approaches that have been proven less effective to guarantee long-term peace (Nkata, 2023). Where there are attempts to incorporate the **non-kinetic** approaches to build capacities, the security personnel are confronted with logistical constraints in their bid to tackle the menace (Uduo, 2025).

11. Lack of a Comprehensive and Effective Security Framework

As reported by Uduo (2025), Nigeria lacks a comprehensive and effective security framework to tackle insurgency and terrorism in its territory. This is due to systemic issues such as corruption, bad leadership, weak institutions, unemployment, and poverty that fuel terrorism and insurgency in the country (Owojori, Fasuan, Ilori, and Matanmi, 2021). The existing frameworks fail to: clearly state the mandate of the MNJTF in the fight against terrorism; discourage over-reliance on force, which leads to human rights violations; provide constant innovations to dislodge the terrorists/insurgents; and promote community support in the area of intelligence sharing (NSS, 2019). This has made the MNJTF struggle in their battle against the terrorists/insurgents with unclear mandates and adaptability, while encouraging the government to rely on the use of force without considering other non-kinetic approaches that

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

could be of help in the fight against the insurgents (Uduo, 2025).

Theoretical Framework

Routine Activity Theory

The main proponents of the Routine Activity Theory are Lawrence Cohen and Marcus Felson (1979). The theory assumes that crime and its perpetrators thrive in societies where there is the availability of motivated offenders, suitable targets, the absence of suitable guardians, and crime opportunities (Cohen and Felson 1979). Where these elements are not available or incomplete, offenders rationally do not choose to embark on criminal activities, probably because of fear of the consequences that may come in the form of punishments if they are caught (Cornish and Clarke 1986). This is why criminologists and crime management experts lay emphasis on crime prevention strategies to deter crime and potential criminals, decrease the number of suitable victims, and increase the presence of control and guardians at all times.

In northern Nigeria, violent conflicts thrive more in areas where there is less presence of security personnel, and a significant number of porous and unpoliced borders, including unpoliced forest areas. This is the situation in some areas in the northern region of the country, where inhabitants are vulnerable because of a lack of adequate security presence. The availability of vast ungoverned spaces makes the region a haven for bandits, terrorists, and insurgents to stay and operate. Also, the availability of livestock in good quantity in a less secure area motivates the bandits to engage in cattle rustling. Also, when they (bandits) lack money, they engage in kidnapping to sustain their livelihoods and also fund their heinous acts. In this case, students, commuters, farmers, and inhabitants of vulnerable areas become suitable targets.

Also, they successfully carry out these attacks because of the absence of suitable guardians who are constitutionally empowered to provide security to lives and property in the country. The lack of security presence in most rural communities in Nigeria has inevitably presented crime opportunities to criminals

such as bandits, criminal herdsmen, and Boko Haram terrorists, who capitalized on the vulnerability of such areas to cause mayhem unabatedly.

Methodology

Survey design was used for this study. Its choice was informed by the exploratory nature of the study, which required the collection of data through questionnaire and interview methods. Other secondary data were obtained through library materials and official records.

Politically, northern Nigeria is made up of 19 states, and out of a total of 774 local government areas existing in Nigeria, the region has a total of 410 (Maikudi, 2019), with an estimated population of 127 million people (StatiSense, 2024; National Population Commission, 2020, cited by the National Bureau of Statistics, 2020).

Purposive sampling was used to select states that are affected by intense violent conflicts in the region based on news reports from various media outlets in recent times. These were: Benue and Plateau (Northcentral); Borno, Yobe, Adamawa (Northeast); and Kaduna, Katsina, Zamfara (Northwest). Because of safety issues, the researcher adopted the online questionnaire method to reach out to the security personnel serving in the selected states for the study.

Since the researcher is a lecturer in a Police Academy, he purposively used his relationship with his past students who are now serving officers of the Nigeria Police Force in the selected states for the study to distribute the questionnaire online among their colleagues who are serving with members of other security agencies in a joint team to control violent conflict in northern Nigeria. They were instructed to restrict the questionnaires to only people who live and work in the affected states, and only to people who have had the experience of violent conflicts in their vicinity.

For the qualitative method, the purposive sampling technique was also adopted to select students who are from the affected communities in the study area to help conduct the in-depth interviews with Unit

Commanders serving in conflict-affected areas in northern Nigeria. To achieve this, an interview guide was designed and was given to the selected students to help conduct the interviews, record the feedback with their phones, and send it through email for easy download, transcription, and analysis.

One hundred and forty-four (144) personnel were selected for this study across the affected states. Out of this number, 128 were considered for questionnaire administration (16 per state), while the remaining 16 were earmarked for the in-depth interview session (2 per state). Therefore, in all, we had a total of 128 persons for the administration of the questionnaire, while 16 were slated for the in-depth interview session, making it a total of 144 respondents selected for the study.

For data collection, the study made use of both quantitative and qualitative instruments. The quantitative instrument used was the questionnaire, while the qualitative instrument was the in-depth interview. Data collected from the respondents were analyzed using the thematic/content analysis method for interview responses, simple percentages for data presentation in tables, while the chi-square statistical tool was used for testing of formulated research hypotheses of the study.

Data Presentation and Analysis

This section deals with the presentation of data, testing of hypotheses, and discussion of findings. From the 144 respondents selected for the study, only 67 (46.53%) responded to the questionnaire, while 5 (31.25%) only responded to the in-depth interview session. The reason for the low rate of responses was due to the fact that most security personnel in the field were not allowed to respond to the questionnaire because of security issues, which required them to speak less about the subject of study. From the distribution of data in Table 1 below, it is indicative that no one responded to the questionnaire from Katsina state among all the security agencies selected for the study. Also, because of fear, most persons contacted refused to respond to the in-depth interview schedules, citing the reason that they do not want to speak to a stranger because of their past experiences, which constituted security risks. Therefore, the data analyses made in this study were derived from the views of the aforementioned number of respondents. The implication is that the data derived did not represent the general view of respondents from all the states selected for the study, particularly those from Katsina state who did not fill out the questionnaire, as shared.

Table 1: Respondents' State/Zone of Operation by Agency

		Security Organization of Respondents					Total
		Nigerian Military	Nigeria Police Force	DSS	NSCDC	Civilian JTF	
Respondents' State of Operation	Benue	0	4	0	1	0	5
	Plateau	2	9	0	0	0	11
	Borno	2	5	0	3	2	12
	Yobe	1	8	0	1	0	10
	Adamawa	1	5	0	0	0	6
	Kaduna	2	7	1	5	1	16
	Zamfara	2	5	0	0	0	7
Total		10	43	1	10	3	67
Respondents' Geopolitical Zone of Operation	North	3	12	0	1	0	16
	Central	5	19	0	5	2	31
	North East	2	12	1	4	1	20
	North West	10	43	1	10	3	67

Source: Researchers' Field Survey, 2025

Table 1 presents the states/zones of operation and agencies of respondents. From the distribution of data, it is apparent that the security personnel from the Nigeria Police Force (64.18%) responded more to the questionnaire. This was because they were more accessible to the researcher, since most of them were his students in the police academy. The DSS (1.49%) had the least, probably because of their secretive nature on sensitive matters that bothers on security. They were closely followed by members of the Civilian JTF (4.48%), probably because of their lower educational status, which may have hindered them from accessing and completing the online questionnaire. However, personnel from the Nigerian Army and the Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corps had the same number of respondents (14.93%).

Furthermore, respondents from Kaduna state had the modal frequency (23.88%), while Adamawa (8.96%) and Zamfara (10.45%) states had the least responses, respectively. This outcome was probably influenced by the number of personnel who had access to the online questionnaire that was shared, and were willing to respond by filling and completing it.

Similarly, the Northeast geopolitical zone had the highest number of respondents (46.27%) who filled out and completed the questionnaire. This outcome was influenced by the fact that all the states (Borno (17.91%), Adamawa (8.96%), and Yobe (14.93%) selected for the study in that zone had personnel who responded to the questionnaire. This made them come out top against the northcentral zone, which had only Benue and Plateau states (23.88%), and the northwest zone, where respondents from Kaduna and Zamfara only contributed for 29.85%. The implication is that, views of respondents from the northeast zone, particularly those of police personnel, dominated the study.

Test of Hypothesis

H₁: The main challenges confronting security agencies in their attempts to control violent

conflict vary significantly in the affected communities of Northern Nigeria.

Ho: The main challenges confronting security agencies in their attempts to control violent conflict do not vary significantly in the affected communities of Northern Nigeria.

In order to test this hypothesis, Question 13 in the questionnaire was used. The question reads: Which of these is the main challenge confronting security personnel in their bid to control violent conflict in your state of operation? The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to calculate the data and test the hypothesis, as seen in Tables 2, 3, and 4 below.

Table 2: Main Challenges Confronting Security Personnel in the Control of Violent Conflict in their States of Operation * Respondents' State of Operation Crosstabulation

Count		Respondents' State of Operation							Total
		Benue	Plateau	Borno	Yobe	Adamawa	Kaduna	Zamfara	
	Corruption	2	4	2	3	2	2	0	15
	Poor Intelligence Gathering/Sharing	1	0	3	1	1	1	2	9
	Lack of Interagency Collaboration among Security Personnel	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	2
	Political Interference	0	4	3	2	0	7	3	19
	Lack of Modern Operational Facilities	1	0	1	1	1	2	2	8
	Lack of Support from Host Community	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	2
	Inadequate Manpower	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
	Poor Welfare	1	1	0	1	0	2	0	5
	Lack of Training on Counter Terrorism/Insurgency	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	3
	Lack of a Comprehensive and Effective Security Framework	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Other	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	2
Total		5	11	12	10	6	16	7	67

Source: Researchers' Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 presents data on the main challenges confronting the security agencies in their attempt to control violent conflict in their state of operation. From the data presented, the issue of political interference (28.36%) stood out as the main challenge. However, it was not an opinion of respondents across all the states - no one in Benue and Adamawa states chose it. Closely followed was the issue of corruption (22.39%). This too was not the opinion of respondents across all states -

respondents from Zamfara state did not choose it. The same happened with the lack of operational facilities (11.94%), which most respondents went for, except those from Plateau state. So, in all, the issue of political interference stood out as the main challenge confronting security personnel in their attempt to control violent conflict in the selected states, but this was not the opinion of respondents in Benue and Adamawa states.

Table 3: Chi-square Contingency Table on the Main Challenge Confronting Security Personnel in the Control of Violent Conflict in their State of Operation

	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
Corruption	15	6.1	8.9
Poor Intelligence Gathering/Sharing	9	6.1	2.9
Lack of Interagency Collaboration among Security Personnel	2	6.1	-4.1
Political Interference	19	6.1	12.9
Lack of Modern Operational Facilities	8	6.1	1.9
Lack of Support from Host Community	2	6.1	-4.1
Inadequate Manpower	1	6.1	-5.1
Poor Welfare	5	6.1	-1.1
Lack of Training on Counter Terrorism/Insurgency	3	6.1	-3.1
Lack of Comprehensive and Effective Security Framework	1	6.1	-5.1
Other	2	6.1	-4.1
Total	67		

Table 4: Chi-square Test on the Main Challenge Confronting Security Personnel in the Control of Violent Conflict in their State of Operation

	Main Challenge Confronting Security Personnel in the Control of Violent Conflict in their State of Operation
Chi-Square	60.896 ^a
Df	10
Asymp. Sig.	.000

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 6.1.

Results

The result obtained from the chi-square test of data indicated that the p-value was less than .05. The outcome was $\chi^2 = (1, N = 67) = 60.896^a$, $df = 10$, $p = .000$. Therefore, the alternate hypothesis which states that the main challenges confronting security agencies in their attempts to control violent conflict vary significantly in the affected communities of Northern Nigeria was accepted, while the null hypothesis was rejected.

Discussion

The presentation, analysis, and testing of research hypotheses made use of data collected from the field. The holistic approach to data formed the basis of the discussion of major findings made in the course of this investigation. This involves analysis of the research hypothesis and other salient discoveries that came into the limelight during personal observation in the field, and when questionnaire and interview responses were analyzed.

From the test of the hypothesis, findings revealed that there is no primary challenge that cuts across all communities of the study. Different communities have their own main challenge, which makes it difficult for the security operatives to control the situation. From the distribution of responses gotten from the security operatives supplying security services against the activities of the perpetrators of violent conflict in northern Nigeria, it was seen that the primary challenges that the majority of the respondents picked, with exemption of some states, are the issues of political interference (28.36% with the exception of Adamawa and Benue states); and corruption (22.3% with the exception of Zamfara state). These findings are in line with the views of the Zamfara state governor,

Dauda Lawal, who stated that political interference from the political class makes the problem of violent conflict linger in the region. According to him, “the military and other security agencies have the capability to take care of these security threats if there is no political interference; the continuous interference from the political class makes the problem linger” (Aleke and Dipo, 2024).

On the issue of corruption, the finding corroborates the view of Gulleng (2025), who submitted that corruption has made it extremely difficult for the Nigerian government to adequately tackle the unending security challenges bedeviling the country for more than two decades now. This manifested in one of the high-profile cases where a former National Security Adviser of the country, Mr Sambo Dasuki, allegedly diverted a sum of \$2billion meant for the acquisition of military equipment for the fight against Boko Haram militants (BBC, 2015).

To corroborate the above submission, data from the in-depth interview session also reflect a multivariate analysis of the main challenges confronting the security personnel in their attempt to control violent conflict in northern Nigeria. According to the respondents:

A lot of problems limit the effectiveness of government responses. Some are gaps in intelligence and early warning. In Nigeria, we are used to reacting after things have happened, rather than being proactive. Also, insufficient resources and manpower. We do not have enough patrol power to cover everywhere at once. Poor coordination and lack of trust and coordination between the police, military, local government, and communities are also factors. Impunity and weak justice processes. When perpetrators are

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

not apprehended or prosecuted, cycles of revenge and further attacks continue (Excerpts from an IDI session with a Unit Commander in Jos, Plateau State, 2025).

In Yobe state, the challenges include: operational difficulties in vast areas, logistics challenges, hardly accessible remote areas, potential sympathy for Boko Haram members, potential local support to the terrorists, etc. These challenges can be a result of poor community policing and security relationships with the members of the community. When people see something, they feel reluctant to report suspicious activities to law enforcement. This leads to more crimes and violent activities in the community (Excerpts from an IDI session with a Unit Commander in Yobe State, 2025).

In Adamawa, the problems are: lack of proper information, lack of good relationships between community members and the security agencies, and issues of security personnel not arriving on time at the crime scene. As an insider, sometimes, we spend up to 12 hours before arriving at the crime scene because of logistical issues. This laxity sometimes leads to serious damage before the arrival of security personnel to help curtail the situation. Also, we have the problem of insufficient firearms, patrol vehicles, and other equipment that aid in curbing crimes and disputes in the community. Overall is the problem of welfare faced by security agencies (Excerpts from an IDI session with a Unit Commander in Adamawa State, 2025).

We have the problem of political interference, poor funding, inadequate modern weapons, false information from informants, and bad governance. Others are: corruption, inadequate manpower, and ineffective training on counter terrorism/insurgency. All these militate against our efforts to control the menace (Excerpts from an IDI session with a Unit Commander in Kaduna State, 2025).

In Borno State, the major problem is sabotage by members of the communities who act as informants to the Boko Haram terrorists. Also, the repentant Boko Haram members who serve as hybrid forces sometimes give false information to the security agencies, which

leads to ambush and the subsequent killing of some security men. So, in a nutshell, some community leaders, local security groupings, and members of the community act as informants to the Boko Haram terrorists, which makes it difficult for us to win the war (Excerpts from an IDI session with a Unit Commander in Borno State, 2025).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study was undertaken to examine the main challenges confronting the security personnel in their attempt to control violent conflict in northern Nigeria. Findings from the study were imperative to conclude that the main challenges militating against the effort of the security agencies to control violent conflicts in northern Nigeria varies depending on the environment where the conflict is taking place, but they include; political interference, corruption, lack of operational facilities, and sabotage from members of the public who serve as informants to terrorists/insurgents. Based on these, the study recommends the following:

1. The government should focus more on identifying the political actors who intervene in the process of law enforcement against the perpetrators of violent conflicts in northern Nigeria. When they are identified, they should be made to face the law in order to serve as a deterrent to others. This is necessary because much has been said about the political actors who sponsor the violent conflicts in the region, but less is heard about their arrest and punishment.
2. The government should make a concerted effort to arrest and punish those involved in corruption, particularly those who divert funds meant for the prosecution of the war against terrorism and insurgency. The legislators at the national assembly should make a law that will make the corrupt officials face life imprisonment when caught and proven by the law, so that it will serve as a deterrent to others.
3. Sophisticated and modern equipment should be supplied to security agencies that are engaged in operations to control violent conflicts in northern Nigeria. It is observed

- that the reason the terrorists and insurgents appear to have an upper hand is that they possess sophisticated weaponry than the law enforcement officers. This is a call for the government to go for the best equipment to empower the security personnel to prosecute the war and win.
4. Also, there is a need for legislation against the act of sabotage by members of the public who collaborate with the terrorists/insurgents against the state. Strong sanctions should be imposed against those identified to be practitioners of such heinous acts. While doing this to serve as a deterrence, the state should also make an effort to reward those who give genuine tips for the apprehension of the terrorists/insurgents to serve as encouragement to others and strengthen community policing.

Declarations

1. **Limitations:** This study had a limitation in the area of data collection. Because of the sensitivity of the topic and the security concerns, most respondents from the study area did not respond to the questionnaire administered and interview schedules as anticipated. Many expressed fear of interacting with a stranger because of their past experiences, and were unwilling to cooperate. The limited responses have an implication on the generalization of findings, because in a state like Katsina, no security personnel responded to the questionnaire. Therefore, the views of other respondents from other states cannot be used to describe the case of Katsina state.

Also, because of the security situation, the researcher did not visit the volatile areas for safety issues. He used his students who graduated from the Nigeria Police Academy and are serving officers in the conflict areas to share an online questionnaire and conduct the in-depth interviews, respectively. This initiative was responsible for the domination of police respondents in the study. Their views influenced the study, and this

signifies bias to other categories of respondents.

2. **Ethical Statement:** This is a survey study. The Nigeria Police Academy Research and Development Committee has confirmed that no ethical approval is required.

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Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

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